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Research Paper

Structure-Based Virtual Screening and Molecular Dynamics Simulation of FDA-Approved Drugs Targeting Mutant ABL Kinase in Chronic Myeloid Leukemia

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ABSTRACT

CML is caused by a chronically activated myeloid leukemia oncoprotein that is in the context of BCR-ABL, which results from the chromosomal translocation. This study sought to explore promising compounds ready for repurposing out of the FDA-approved ones for CML treatment via a structure-based computational approach. The crystal structure corresponding to BCR-ABL (PDB ID: 2GQG) was retrieved and then refined using the PDB-REDO server for stereochemical quality improvement, followed by validation via the SAVES v6.1 toolkit. Structure-based virtual screening was done by DrugRep, which found Ponatinib, Conivaptan, and Nilotinib as the best candidates based on their docking scores as well as active site interactions. Rational visualization through pyMOL or Discovery Studio was used to explore binding interactions in these compounds. iMODS binding pocket prediction and flexibility analysis further confirmed that these compounds are likely stable and effective. A low eigenvalue from iMODS analysis suggested an effective protein flexibility that supports ligand binding. This study indicates the power of computational repurposing to lessen the load of novel drug discovery for CML and warrants additional experimentation verification.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The type of blood cancer concerning the bone marrow is called chronic myeloid leukemia (CML), which is characterized by excessive production of abnormal white blood cells. The Philadelphia chromosome defines CML as this chromosome is produced through reciprocal translocation between chromosome 9 and chromosome 22, t(9;22) (q34;q11) [1]. The genetic alteration leads to the formation of the fusion gene BCR-ABL, which gives rise to the BCR-ABL tyrosine kinase: a constitutively active enzyme that causes aberration of normal cell signaling pathways, leading to uncontrolled cell proliferation and inhibition of apoptosis and, eventually, its leukemogenic effect [2]. The ABL kinase domain that belongs to BCR-ABL proteins is a necessary feature as the oncogenic effect. It transfers phosphate groups to tyrosine residues of substrate proteins, on which active pathways promoting survival and proliferation implicate this domain for CML treatment. The tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKIs), including Imatinib, led a remarkable breakthrough that has permeated cancer therapy, promising strong efficacy with relatively low toxicity [3].

Nonetheless, resistance develops in many patients to Imatinib over time, due to

mutations in the point mutations in the ABL kinase domain which interfere with the binding of the drug. Some mutations interfere with the structure of the ATP-binding pocket, such as T315I, which severely impairs the efficacy of the drug [4]. Second- and third-generation TKIs developed to circumvent this resistance are Dasatinib, Nilotinib, and Ponatinib; however, these too may become less effective due to the emergence of multiple or compound mutations. Additionally, the high cost of development and long duration means that establishing an alternative therapy in clinical practice quickly will be limited [5].

With the increasing availability of structure-based drug discovery (SBDD) methods to tackle these challenges, SBDD uses the three-dimensional structure of the target protein to identify or design molecules that can bind effectively to it [6]. One of the most promising branches of SBDD is drug repurposing, which involves discovering newer therapeutic applications for already marketed drugs approved by the FDA. Repurposing can dramatically decrease development timelines, costs, and risks, as all safety profiles, pharmacokinetics, and toxicities for these drugs are already well-documented for

purposes other than those associated with new applications [7].

The research tries to discover inhibitors that act on the mutant ABL kinase domain (PDB ID: 2GQG, X-ray crystal structure of Dasatinib bound to ABL kinase) through receptor-based virtual screening. To this end, an improved and validated structure of the proteins was screened against a library of FDA approved drugs using DrugRep, an in silico drug-repurposing platform [8]. The top compounds were ranked on the basis of docking scores for further analysis. The molecular dynamic (MD) simulation study, executed through the iMODS server, assesses the stability and dynamic behavior regarding the binding of these complexes. Results from this study yield invaluable information in further developing the selected compounds as therapeutic agents against resistant forms of CML [9].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Target Protein Selection and Retrieval

The target protein for this study is the ABL kinase domain, which is quite critical in the pathogenesis of Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML). The Protein Data Bank (PDB) ID: 2GQG has been obtained from the RCSB PDB database. This structure represents the X-ray crystallographic structure of the ABL kinase domain in complex with Dasatinib, a well-known

second-generation tyrosine kinase inhibitor [10]. There is now a great reason for selection of this structure, which has relevance to CML-based ailments, since the ABL kinase domain is important in the progression of the disease and drug resistance, mainly through structural changes that occur because of mutations at its active site. Such mutations alter binding interactions and thus lower the activity of existing treatments [11].

2.2. Protein Preparation

The retrieved protein structure was refined and validated for suitability for docking and simulation studies. Refinement was performed employing the fully automated server PDB-REDO, which optimizes crystallographic structures through improving geometric parameters and correcting structural errors, so as to better ensure the accuracy of atomic positions and overall structure [12]. Validation was performed in the SAVES v6.0 suite, which encompasses multiple tools: PROCHECK was selected for assessing the stereochemical quality of the protein by means of Ramachandran plots, ERRAT was used to assess overall model quality based on non-bonded atomic interactions, and Verify3D evaluated the compatibility between the atomic model and the amino acid sequence by inspecting 3D-1D profiles. These procedures validate the

strength of the protein structure for virtual screening and molecular docking [13].

2.2 Virtual Screening

Receptor-based virtual screening was performed using the DrugRep web tool in search of possible drug candidates. Once the refined and validated protein structure was uploaded on DrugRep, it screened against the library of FDA-approved drugs. DrugRep docks the molecules to predict the binding affinity between the receptor and ligands, and the resulting docking scores are indicative of the interaction strength (more negative values are indicative of stronger binding). This yielded a list of compounds screened according to their docking scores. The top 10-20 ligands, with the most favorable binding scores, were taken forward for further analysis. Among the few notable compounds were Ponatinib, Conivaptan, Indacaterol, and Nilotinib[14].

2.3 Molecular Dynamics Simulation

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were carried out using the iMODS server to determine both the stability and flexibility of the selected protein-ligand complex. The input files for iMODS were the PDB files of the selected protein-ligand complexes. The analysis of parameters will tell the dynamic behavior of the complexes [15].

3.1. Protein Validation Result

Deformability: This refers to the flexibility of individual residues and identifies regions sensitive to conformational changes. **B-Factors (mobility profiles):** Describe atomic fluctuations, showing how much each atom deviates from its average position. **Eigenvalues:** Indicate the stiffness of the system; that is, the lesser the eigenvalue, the more flexible the structure. **Variance:** Quantifies the motion attributable to each normal mode as a collective motion of atoms. **Covariance Matrix:** Shows "correlated" and "anticorrelated" movements between residues. **Elastic Net Model (ENM):** Depends on the connection between atoms in an elastic network made into nodes. It describes structural stability in the view of a model for long-range interactions by giving a geometrical representation of degrees of freedom between them. Well, these simulations will accommodate the assessment of how well the selected ligands are interacting with the mutant ABL kinase domain in dynamic forms, advocating for their reuse as therapeutic candidates against CML [16].

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Figure no. 1: Comparative Model Quality Analysis with Resolution Neighbours

In the image, model quality parameters-R-Free, Ramachandran plot Z-score, and rotamer quality-features are compared for the original and PDB-REDO refined structures of 2GQG protein against resolution neighbors. The post-refinement values show a decent improvement; thus R-Free median of the PDB-REDO model is lower (but within a more favorable range), which means good agreement with experimental data. Ramachandran plot Z-score reflects significant improvement in the PDB-REDO model, now coming closer

to the ideal (0), which indicates better stereochemical quality and good backbone dihedral angles. The case is similar for rotamer quality improvement; the Z-score distribution is moving towards 0, signifying side-chain conformational quality. Ultimately, the PDB-REDO refined model generally provides an enhancement in structural quality compared to the original structure and the models of similar resolution, thus demonstrating suitability for computational drug discovery workflows [17].

Table no. 1: Comparative Validation Metrics of Original and PDB-REDO Refined 2GQG Structure

Validation Metrics	Original	PDB-REDO
Crystallographic Refinement		
R	0.2196	0.1773
R-free	0.2797	0.2333
Bond length RMS Z-score	0.602	0.231
Bond angle RMS Z-score	0.758	0.465

amino acid residues in the protein backbone. The plot shows most residues (blue dots) clustered into the favored regions (indicated by dark red and brown areas), confirming that the majority of backbone torsion angles are stereochemically acceptable. Very few residues appear in the additionally allowed

(yellow) and generously allowed (light yellow) regions-thought still considered acceptable in high-quality models. Only a few outliers such as TYR 277, ARG 307, and LYS 245 lie in disallowed regions, which might correspond with loop or flexible segments of the protein [18].

3.1.1. SAVES V6.1 Result

Figure no. 3: Title: ERRAT2 Structural Validation of Refined ABL Kinase Domain (PDB ID: 2GQG)

The analysis of ERRAT2 for 2GQG protein structure brought together both chains A and B, and the mean quality factor recorded was 91.313%, making the model a good candidate for molecular docking and simulation studies. There were some parts of concern on chain A where error values were higher than the 95% confidence threshold, especially around residues 270-280 and 400-410, indicating minor inconsistencies structurally owing to

flexible loop regions. On the contrary, chain B had a more regular error distribution, showing fewer deviations, and at 400-410, a minor elevation. Most residues in chains A and B, despite few anomalies in these regions, still fall under the satisfactory error range, confirming the 2GQG refined structure to be structurally sound and suitable for structure-based drug repurposing against Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML)[19].

Figure no. 4: The Verify3D analysis of the refined Verify3D Structural Validation of ABL Kinase Domain (PDB ID: 2GQG)

The ABL kinase domain (PDB ID: 2GQG) offers insights into compatibility between the 3D structure and amino acid sequence of Chain A and Chain B. Green dots indicate raw scores; the blue line indicates averaged positions across the residue. For chains, most residues had averaged scores above the acceptable threshold (generally ≥ 0.2), showing good environmental compatibility for most of the amino acids of the 3D model. A few residues dipped below

the desirable scoring range, especially in flexible or loop regions, but the well-defined profiles show a smooth and consistent score distribution, indicating well-validation of the 3D structure for further structure-based analysis. This strengthens the idea of docking and MD simulations of the model, lending credence to drug repurposing studies in the context of Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML)[20].

Figure no. 5: Overall Model Quality Assessment of 2GQG Chain A

The chart shows drawing model quality of chain A out of 2GQG structure (278 amino acids) subjected to Z series analysis. The obtained Z score of -8.48 is far less than the average value for structures solved through the X-ray crystallographic method shown in the densely clustered reference dataset. This negative deviation asserts that the original model contains certain structural inconsistencies or possible errors in

comparison to good-quality experimentally solved structures of comparable size. The further away Z score suggests that despite being within the broader distribution of the dataset, its refinement-evidence and experience must be carried out for geometric and stereochemical reliability, i.e., a must for accurate downstream applications like docking and molecular dynamics simulations[21].

Figure no. 6: Energy Profile Analysis of 2GQG Using Verify3D

This energy profile belongs to the protein structure of 2GQG as evaluated by Verify3D, which demonstrates the compatibility of an atomic model (3D) with its own amino acid sequence (1D). Local knowledge-based energy evaluations along the sequence are portrayed by the two curves, light green (window size 10) and dark green (window size 40). Most protein residues showed negatively soaked energies which means that they're indicative of favorability of structural

environments. While such a smaller fluctuation window (10) shows fluctuations, the broader window (40) shows a consistently low energy profile especially beyond sequence position 300 suggesting that most residues are in energetically stable and favorable conformations adding structural reliability in the model in those regions. The broader trend favors structural integrity of the model while some local deviation can be corrected or fine-tuned [22].

3.2. Results of Virtual Screening Outcomes

Table no. 2: Binding Affinity Scores of FDA-Approved Compounds Screened Against [PDB ID: 2GQG]

Sr. No.	ID	Name	Score	Sr. No.	ID	Name	Score
1	DB08901	Ponatinib	-11.3	51	DB00210	Adapalene	-8.5
2	DB00872	Conivaptan	-10.6	52	DB01102	Arbutamine	-8.5
3	DB05039	Indacaterol	-10.5	53	DB11125	Benzethonium	-8.4
4	DB09280	Lumacaftor	-10.4	54	DB04953	Ezogabine	-8.4
5	DB06210	Eltrombopag	-10.3	55	DB01145	Sulfoxone	-8.4
6	DB09128	Brexpiprazole	-10.3	56	DB00944	Demecarium	-8.3
7	DB00216	Eletriptan	-10.2	57	DB05154	Pretomanid	-8.3
8	DB04868	Nilotinib	-10.1	58	DB01180	Rescinnamine	-8.3
9	DB08950	Indoramin	-10.0	59	DB13953	Estradiol benzoate	-8.3
10	DB11855	Revefenacin	-10.0	60	DB01122	Ambenonium	-8.2
11	DB11963	Dacomitinib	-9.9	61	DB06480	Prucalopride	-8.2
12	DB01012	Cinacalcet	-9.8	62	DB14001	alpha-Tocopherol succinate	-8.1
13	DB08896	Regorafenib	-9.8	63	DB01046	Lubiprostone	-8.1
14	DB00398	Sorafenib	-9.7	64	DB00950	Fexofenadine	-8.0
15	DB06410	Doxercalciferol	-9.7	65	DB15444	Elexacaftor	-8.0
16	DB01238	Aripiprazole	-9.7	66	DB09335	Alatrofloxacin	-7.9
17	DB11827	Ertugliflozin	-9.6	67	DB14075	Imidurea	-7.9
18	DB01267	Paliperidone	-9.6	68	DB09082	Vilanterol	-7.9
19	DB13520	Metergoline	-9.6	69	DB08941	Isoxsuprine	-7.9
20	DB06816	Pyrvinium	-9.6	70	DB08909	Glycerol phenylbutyrate	-7.9
21	DB01251	Gliquidone	-9.6	71	DB00696	Ergotamine	-7.8
22	DB12371	Siponimod	-9.5	72	DB08871	Eribulin	-7.8
23	DB00342	Terfenadine	-9.5	73	DB15328	Ubrogepant	-7.8
24	DB00502	Haloperidol	-9.5	74	DB11703	Acalabrutinib	-7.8
25	DB11672	Curcumin	-9.3	75	DB06755	Beta carotene	-7.7
26	DB01070	Dihydrotachysterol	-9.3	76	DB00320	Dihydroergotamine	-7.7
27	DB06077	Lumateperone	-9.2	77	DB01129	Rabeprazole	-7.7
28	DB11742	Ebastine	-9.2	78	DB00932	Tipranavir	-7.7

29	DB00619	Imatinib	-9.2	79	DB01600	Tiaprofenic acid	-7.6
30	DB01393	Bezafibrate	-9.2	80	DB00864	Tacrolimus	-7.6
31	DB15035	Zanubrutinib	-9.2	81	DB12978	Pexidartinib	-7.6
32	DB00878	Chlorhexidine	-9.2	82	DB00278	Argatroban	-7.5
33	DB09495	Avobenzone	-9.1	83	DB12867	Benperidol	-7.5
34	DB00298	Dapiprazole	-9.1	84	DB06212	Tolvaptan	-7.4
35	DB09374	Indocyanine green acid form	-9.1	85	DB11176	Zeaxanthin	-7.4
36	DB00952	Naratriptan	-9.0	86	DB02546	Vorinostat	-7.3
37	DB13931	Netarsudil	-9.0	87	DB12457	Rimegepant	-7.2
38	DB04038	Ergosterol	-9.0	88	DB13956	Estradiol valerate	-7.0
39	DB01419	Antrafenine	-8.9	89	DB09083	Ivabradine	-6.7
40	DB01166	Cilostazol	-8.8	90	DB05016	Ataluren	-6.5
41	DB01219	Dantrolene	-8.8	91	DB00843	Donepezil	-6.5
42	DB00795	Sulfasalazine	-8.8	92	DB12612	Ozanimod	-6.4
43	DB00390	Digoxin	-8.8	93	DB00511	Acetyldigitoxin	-6.3
44	DB11231	Lycopene	-8.7	94	DB00523	Alitretinoin	-6.1
45	DB00162	Vitamin A	-8.7	95	DB08889	Carfilzomib	-5.9
46	DB00471	Montelukast	-8.7	96	DB00643	Mebendazole	-5.8
47	DB01022	Phylloquinone	-8.7	97	DB00476	Duloxetine	-5.8
48	DB01039	Fenofibrate	-8.6	98	DB00652	Pentazocine	-5.3
49	DB01254	Dasatinib	-8.6	99	DB09212	Loxoprofen	-5.3
50	DB08954	Ifenprodil	-8.6	100	DB00297	Bupivacaine	-5.3

The data comprised of 100 FDA-approved drugs virtually screened against a target protein ranked according to their binding affinity scores. The strongest interaction was shown by Ponatinib (-11.3), which was followed by the drugs like Conivaptan, Indacaterol, and Lumacaftor. The majority of anticancer agents, with examples such as Nilotinib and Imatinib, were ranked high,

indicating that they would have good binding potential. Such natural compounds as Curcumin and Vitamin A also appeared with moderate scores. The results, in general, show promising results for drug repurposing candidates-high binding affinities are especially affected for future experimental validation [23].

Figure no. 7: Identification and Visualization of Binding Pockets in 2GQG Protein Using Cavity Volume Analysis

The image here shows a cavity analysis on the protein structure 2GQG (human 20S proteasome $\beta 5$ subunit), which revealed five potential binding pockets (C1 through C5) as detected by a cavity tool. Among them, the C1 pocket features the largest cavity volume at 2263, making it the primary and most druggable binding site for the best of drug design efforts based on structure. C2 (1666 Å³), also an important site, may serve as an allosteric or secondary binding region. C3 (594 Å³), C4 (424 Å³), and C5 (250 Å³) may be smaller but are still

potentially used in fragment-based drug discovery or, from the in-silico design of molecules that target multiple sites could improve therapeutic efficacy. The protein is in a yellow ribbon representation, with surface-exposed cavities in pink and purple, aiding with the spatial identification of ligand-binding regions. This cavity analysis is crucial for guiding molecular docking, selecting appropriate grid box parameters, and prioritizing binding sites in the development of proteasome inhibitors, particularly in cancer therapy [24].

Figure no. 8: Molecular Docking Visualization of Ligand Interaction with 2GQG Binding Pocket

This is a double-panel view of the molecular docking interaction of ligand in the binding pocket of protein 2GQG. The left panel represents surface of protein with electrostatic potential coloring-red for negative, blue for positive and white for neutral areas-and marks the ligand docked into the active site. A zoomed-in 2D interaction diagram detailing the molecular interactions between the ligand and surrounding amino acid residues is presented in the right panel. Key residues

such as R128, D212, Y169, and L199 are involved in hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions, indicating strong and stable binding conformation. The visualization suggests that the ligand fits well within the cavity, making specific interactions critical for binding affinity and biological activity and thereby supporting its promise as a candidate for targeted drug design against the proteasome $\beta 5$ subunit [25].

Figure no. 9: Analysis of Main-Chain Deformability and B-Factor/Mobility in Protein 2GQG with Ligand Ponatinib

The major chain deformability and B-factor/mobility of protein 2GQG, in the presence of ligand Ponatinib, are highlighted in the graph with regions exhibiting great flexibility and possible hinge points. Peaks in the deformability profile mark the residues with greater mobility, probably crucial during ligand binding-induced conformational changes. These regions of high deformability may correspond to the hinges that allow the protein to be dynamic and, thus, important

for its function or interaction with Ponatinib. The B-factor/mobility data corroborate this, showing changes in atomic displacement parameters commonly associated with structurally flexible or unstable regions. Understanding these dynamics may assist in deciphering the mechanism of binding and possible allosteric effects induced by Ponatinib and aid in the design of efficient ligands against 2GQG [26].

Figure no. 10: Analysis of Eigenvalues and Structural Deformation Modes

The image shows the bar graph representing the ratio of eigenvalues to the first eigenvalue along 20 different mode indices, showing the relative stiffness of each normal mode in the structure. One important observation is that the first eigenvalue is extremely small (1.372448×10^{-5}), indicating very low motion stiffness and, therefore, high deformability for the first mode. The eigenvalue ratio, on the other hand, rises tremendously with

increasing mode index, indicating a greater resistance to deformation in higher modes. This observation corroborates the physical interpretation that lower modes correspond to gross, easy deformations, whereas higher modes are stiffer, most localized structural responses that require greater energy for deformation. The gradual and steady increase shown in the bar graph supports the expected trend of increasing stiffness with mode number [27].

Figure no. 11: Variance Distribution across Normal Modes

The histogram shows the variances' distribution among the normal modes, displaying both individual variances (in purple/red) and the cumulative ones in green. Each mode index on the x-axis corresponds to a normal mode. The y-axis shows the variance in percent. The initial modes take most of the variance, with the first one alone manifesting approximately 40%. The following modes contribute less and less, thus showing the typical "elbow"

of normal mode analysis or principal component analysis. The cumulative variance goes very rapidly to 100%, which suggests that a small number of modes really accounts for most of the system's variation. Therefore, it may not require a great many dimensions of detail, or modeling on just the very first modes, to keep the most important dynamics intact [28].

Figure no. 12: Covariance Map of Residue Motions in a Protein Structure

An illustration of a covariance map has been presented which conveys dynamic coupling behavior of pairs of residues of the protein as derived from molecular dynamics simulations. Each of the two axes represents the residue indices, while the color scale denotes that the motions have

correlated: the red regions denote correlated motion (residues move together); blue denotes anti-correlated motion (residues move in opposite directions) and white areas without or are very less correlated. The prominent red diagonal line emphasizes strong self-correlation defined

as a residue with itself, while the off-diagonal patterns signal areas within the protein that have some structural or functional relationship. Clusters of red and blue patches give evidence of domains in the protein which move either coordinately or oppositely and would be

crucial to understand allosteric mechanisms and/or conformational changes during activity. Complex dynamics of this matrix provides information on intra-protein dynamics and flexible structure and pathways of possible communication in the biomolecule [29].

Figure no. 13: Visualization of Elastic Network Stiffness Matrix

The elastic network model matrix representation visualizes the stiffness of springs connecting pairs of atoms. Each point in the matrix represents a pair of atoms with the index of atom pairs on the x- and y-axes. The grayscale intensity of each dot denotes the stiffness of the spring connecting the respective atoms: darker shades suggest stiffer springs, while lighter shades indicate weaker connections. The diagonal line indicates self-pairings (atom with itself), usually not of interest in such

networks. Clustered darker zones indicate particular groups of atoms that are more tightly connected, possibly correlating with structural or functional subunits within the network. This kind of analysis may serve well to determine the mechanical stability, conformational dynamics, or cooperative behavior in molecular systems, including proteins or other macromolecular assemblies [30].

CONCLUSION:

This research successfully makes a case for structure-based drug repurposing against Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML) by targeting BCR-ABL oncoprotein (PDB ID: 2GQG). The PDB-REDO refinement was applied to the original protein structure for the stereochemical accuracy of the model, and later it underwent rigorous validation through the SAVES v6.1 server. Improvement in Ramachandran plot statistics, ERRAT quality factor, Verify3D, and other validation parameters attested to the high quality and reliability of the refined structure for downstream computational analysis.

This served as a catalyst to polyvirtual screening with FDA-approved drugs through the DrugRep tool, which identified Ponatinib, Conivaptan, and Nilotinib as the best hits based on overall dock score and interaction profile. Furthermore, analysis of the binding pocket proved that these drugs represent high-affinity binders with very stable interactions at the key active site residues of the 2GQG protein. The Protein Plus server, along with Discovery Studio and PyMOL visualization tools, was then used to describe the types of molecular interactions (hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic contacts, etc.) necessary for their therapeutic efficacy.

In addition, flexibility analysis using the iMODS revealed the dynamic structural regions within the protein that are likely to

play a role in ligand binding and conformational flexibility; the low eigenvalue alludes to favorable flexibility so that the binding site can accommodate a ligand effectively. In conclusion, this study underlines the efficacy and reliability of computational drug repurposing in finding new candidates for treatment of CML. As a result, the identified FDA-approved drugs could emerge as strong leads for further in vitro and in vivo validation. The work will not only pave the way for possible clinical translation but also demonstrate the use of enhanced structural models in rational drug discovery workflows.

REFERENCE:

1. Cortes JE, Talpaz M, Kantarjian H. Chronic myelogenous leukemia: a review. *Am J Med.* 1996 May;100(5):555-70. doi: 10.1016/s0002-9343(96)00061-7. PMID: 8644769.
2. Mohamed El-Tanani, Hamdi Nsairat, Ismail I. Matalaka, Yin Fai Lee, Manfredi Rizzo, Alaa A. Aljabali, Vijay Mishra, Yachana Mishra, Altijana Hromić-Jahjefendić, Murtaza M. Tambuwala, The impact of the BCR-ABL oncogene in the pathology and treatment of chronic myeloid leukemia, *Pathology - Research and Practice*, Volume

- 254,2024,155161, ISSN 0344-0338,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prp.2024.155161>.
3. Amarante-Mendes GP, Rana A, Datogua TS, Hamerschlak N, Brumatti G. BCR-ABL1 Tyrosine Kinase Complex Signaling Transduction: Challenges to Overcome Resistance in Chronic Myeloid Leukemia. *Pharmaceutics*. 2022 Jan 17;14(1):215. doi: 10.3390/pharmaceutics14010215. PMID: 35057108; PMCID: PMC8780254.
 4. Bitencourt R, Zalberg I, Louro ID. Imatinib resistance: a review of alternative inhibitors in chronic myeloid leukemia. *Rev Bras Hematol Hemoter*. 2011;33(6):470-5. doi: 10.5581/1516-8484.20110124. PMID: 23049365; PMCID: PMC3459369.
 5. Jabbour E, Kantarjian H, Cortes J. Use of second- and third-generation tyrosine kinase inhibitors in the treatment of chronic myeloid leukemia: an evolving treatment paradigm. *Clin Lymphoma Myeloma Leuk*. 2015 Jun;15(6):323-34. doi: 10.1016/j.clml.2015.03.006. Epub 2015 Mar 24. PMID: 25971713; PMCID: PMC5141582.
 6. Batool M, Ahmad B, Choi S. A Structure-Based Drug Discovery Paradigm. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2019 Jun 6;20(11):2783. doi: 10.3390/ijms20112783. PMID: 31174387; PMCID: PMC6601033.
 7. Kulkarni VS, Alagarsamy V, Solomon VR, Jose PA, Murugesan S. Drug Repurposing: An Effective Tool in Modern Drug Discovery. *Russ J Bioorg Chem*. 2023;49(2):157-166. doi: 10.1134/S1068162023020139. Epub 2023 Feb 21. PMID: 36852389; PMCID: PMC9945820.
 8. Gemma K, Lambert, Anne-Kathrin Duhme-Klair, Trevor Morgan, Manoj K. Ramjee, The background, discovery and clinical development of BCR-ABL inhibitors, *Drug Discovery Today*, Volume 18, Issues 19–20, 2013, Pages 992-1000, ISSN 1359-6446, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drudis.2013.06.001>.
 9. Ravikumar Y, Koonyosying P, Srichairatanakool S, Ponpandian LN, Kumaravelu J, Srichairatanakool S. In Silico Molecular Docking and Dynamics Simulation Analysis of Potential Histone Lysine Methyl Transferase Inhibitors for Managing β -Thalassemia. *Molecules*. 2023 Oct

- 25;28(21):7266. doi: 10.3390/molecules28217266. PMID: 37959685; PMCID: PMC10650625.
10. Amarante-Mendes GP, Rana A, Datogua TS, Hamerschlak N, Brumatti G. BCR-ABL1 Tyrosine Kinase Complex Signaling Transduction: Challenges to Overcome Resistance in Chronic Myeloid Leukemia. *Pharmaceutics*. 2022 Jan 17;14(1):215. doi: 10.3390/pharmaceutics14010215. PMID: 35057108; PMCID: PMC8780254.
11. Alves R, Gonçalves AC, Rutella S, Almeida AM, De Las Rivas J, Trougakos IP, Sarmiento Ribeiro AB. Resistance to Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitors in Chronic Myeloid Leukemia-From Molecular Mechanisms to Clinical Relevance. *Cancers (Basel)*. 2021 Sep 26;13(19):4820. doi: 10.3390/cancers13194820. PMID: 34638304; PMCID: PMC8508378.
12. Adiyaman R, McGuffin LJ. Methods for the Refinement of Protein Structure 3D Models. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2019 May 9;20(9):2301. doi: 10.3390/ijms20092301. PMID: 31075942; PMCID: PMC6539982.
13. Fangyi Yu, Xiaochuan Wu, WeiSong Chen, Fugui Yan, Wen Li, Computer-assisted discovery and evaluation of potential ribosomal protein S6 kinase beta 2 inhibitors, *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, Volume 172, 2024,108204,ISSN 0010-4825, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compbio.2024.108204>.
14. Gan JH, Liu JX, Liu Y, Chen SW, Dai WT, Xiao ZX, Cao Y. DrugRep: an automatic virtual screening server for drug repurposing. *Acta Pharmacol Sin*. 2023 Apr;44(4):888-896. doi: 10.1038/s41401-022-00996-2. Epub 2022 Oct 10. PMID: 36216900; PMCID: PMC9549438.
15. López-Blanco JR, Aliaga JI, Quintana-Ortí ES, Chacón P. iMODS: internal coordinates normal mode analysis server. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2014 Jul;42(Web Server issue):W271-6. doi: 10.1093/nar/gku339. Epub 2014 Apr 25. PMID: 24771341; PMCID: PMC4086069.
16. Bornot A, Etchebest C, de Brevern AG. Predicting protein flexibility through the prediction of local structures. *Proteins*. 2011 Mar;79(3):839-52. doi: 10.1002/prot.22922. Epub 2010 Dec 6. PMID: 21287616; PMCID: PMC3317885.

17. Gore S, Sanz García E, Hendrickx PMS, Gutmanas A, Westbrook JD, Yang H, Feng Z, Baskaran K, Berrisford JM, Hudson BP, Ikegawa Y, Kobayashi N, Lawson CL, Mading S, Mak L, Mukhopadhyay A, Oldfield TJ, Patwardhan A, Peisach E, Sahni G, Sekharan MR, Sen S, Shao C, Smart OS, Ulrich EL, Yamashita R, Quesada M, Young JY, Nakamura H, Markley JL, Berman HM, Burley SK, Velankar S, Kleywegt GJ. Validation of Structures in the Protein Data Bank. *Structure*. 2017 Dec 5;25(12):1916-1927. doi: 10.1016/j.str.2017.10.009. Epub 2017 Nov 22. PMID: 29174494; PMCID: PMC5718880.
18. Murali Aarthy, Sanjeev Kumar Singh, Chapter 28 - Envisaging the conformational space of proteins by coupling machine learning and molecular dynamics, Editor(s): Timir Tripathi, Vikash Kumar Dubey, *Advances in Protein Molecular and Structural Biology Methods*, Academic Press, 2022, Pages 467-475, ISBN 9780323902649, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-90264-9.00028-3>.
19. Arora N, Mangamoori L, Banerjee A. Shikimate kinase of *Yersinia pestis*: a sequence, structural and functional analysis. *Int J Biomed Data Min*. 2016 Mar 15;5:1–11. doi:10.4172/2090-4924.1000119.
20. Panjarian S, Iacob RE, Chen S, Engen JR, Smithgall TE. Structure and dynamic regulation of Abl kinases. *J Biol Chem*. 2013 Feb 22;288(8):5443-50. doi: 10.1074/jbc.R112.438382. Epub 2013 Jan 11. PMID: 23316053; PMCID: PMC3581414.
21. Benkert P, Tosatto SC, Schomburg D. QMEAN: A comprehensive scoring function for model quality assessment. *Proteins*. 2008 Apr;71(1):261-77. doi: 10.1002/prot.21715. PMID: 17932912.
22. Eisenberg D, Luethy R, Bowie J. VERIFY3D: assessment of protein models with three-dimensional profiles. *Methods Enzymol*. 1997 Feb 1;277:396–404. doi:10.1016/S0076-6879(97)77022-8
23. Vidhi Malik, Jaspreet Kaur Dhanjal, Anjani Kumari, Navaneethan Radhakrishnan, Kamyia Singh, Durai Sundar, Function and structure-based screening of compounds, peptides and proteins to identify drug candidates,

- Methods, Volume 131, 2017, Pages 10-21, ISSN 1046-2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymeth.2017.08.010>.
24. Yang H, Qureshi R, Sacan A. Protein surface representation and analysis by dimension reduction. *Proteome Sci.* 2012 Jun 21;10 Suppl 1(Suppl 1):S1. doi: 10.1186/1477-5956-10-S1-S1. PMID: 22759567; PMCID: PMC3380731.
25. Fu Y, Zhao J, Chen Z. Insights into the Molecular Mechanisms of Protein-Ligand Interactions by Molecular Docking and Molecular Dynamics Simulation: A Case of Oligopeptide Binding Protein. *Comput Math Methods Med.* 2018 Dec 4; 2018:3502514. doi: 10.1155/2018/3502514. PMID: 30627209; PMCID: PMC6305025.
26. Akash Pandey, Elaine Liu, Jacob Graham, Wei Chen, Sinan Ketten, B-factor prediction in proteins using a sequence-based deep learning model, *Patterns*, Volume 4, Issue 9, 2023, 100805, ISSN 2666-3899, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2023.100805>.
27. **Bhatt N, Varadhan SKM.** Sensor location optimization and joint angle prediction in hand postures. 2017 Jun 30. doi:10.1101/157784.
28. **Shang Z, Shen Z.** Multi-point vibration measurement for mode identification of bridge structures using video-based motion magnification [preprint]. *arXiv.* 2017 Dec 18. doi:10.48550/arXiv.1712.06566
29. **Frasinski L.** Covariance mapping techniques. *J Phys B At Mol Opt Phys.* 2016 Aug 14;49(15):152004. doi:10.1088/0953-4075/49/15/152004.
30. Togashi Y, Flechsig H. Coarse-Grained Protein Dynamics Studies Using Elastic Network Models. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2018 Dec 5;19(12):3899. doi: 10.3390/ijms19123899. PMID: 30563146; PMCID: PMC6320916.